

Study of 3D printing process: Optimization, quality analysis, and comparison of 3D printed and cast ceramic properties

Adam Boleslavský ^a *, Hana Ovčáčiková ^b, Milan Mihola ^a, Aki Mikkola ^c, Michaela Topinková ^b, Zdenko Bobovský ^a

^a VSB – Technical University of Ostrava, Faculty of Mechanical, Engineering, Department of Robotics, 17. listopadu 2172/15, 708 00 Ostrava - Poruba, Czech Republic

^b Technical University of Ostrava, Faculty of Materials Science and Technology, Department of Thermal Engineering, 17. listopadu 2172/15, 708 00 Ostrava - Poruba, Czech Republic

^c Mechanical Engineering, LUT School of Energy Systems, Yliopistonkatu 34, Lappeenranta, Finland

ARTICLE INFO

Dataset link: zenodo.org/records/14161699

Keywords:

Additive manufacturing(AM)
Direct ink writing (DIW)
Ceramic
3D printing methodology
Clay

ABSTRACT

The goal of this study was to optimize and validate the procedures and methods used to form ceramic objects using 3D-print molding instead of cast molding. Chamotte refractory clay was shaped into 5 x 5 x 5 cm cubes using both the 3D-print-molding and cast-molding methods. These cubes were then evaluated, fired, and evaluated again. The 3D-print molding method used was an adaptation of 'direct ink writing'. Since refractory clay dries during manufacturing, a Photoneo 3D scanner was used to monitor cube shrinkage before firing. Other basic properties such as mineralogical composition, evaluated via X-ray diffraction, were also measured. X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy determined chemical composition. After firing, compressive strength, bulk density, porosity, and water absorption were measured and structural aspects such as cracking and porosity were evaluated. The 3D-print molding of the chamotte clay was largely successful. The measured compressive strength of the fired 3D-print-molded and cast-molded ceramic cubes was 31.4 MPa and 30.4 MPa, respectively. The 3D-print-molded ceramic parts were slightly more porous (14.5%) and absorptive (7.1%). Total volumetric shrinkage was 36 %. Detailed cross-sectional analysis of the samples identified defects related to specific shortcomings of both molding methods. This information suggests areas that could be targeted for refinement. Addressing them could lead to significant advancements, allowing 3D-print-molded ceramics and similar materials to achieve superior properties compared to conventional manufacturing methods.

1. Introduction

Three-Dimensional (3D) printing, also referred to as additive manufacturing, has brought about a small revolution in technology while significantly impacting materials science. The main advantages it brings include rapid prototyping, design flexibility, high precision, time savings, cost-effectiveness, and variability of the printing materials [1]. For example in these studies [1,2], the authors reported their expectation that the world's additive manufacturing market would reach approximately \$8.6 billion by 2020. In fact, revenues in 2018 were \$14.5 billion, almost double their expectation.

3D printing has been under development since 1981, when Hideo Kodama pioneered a solution for rapid prototyping [3]. Kodama's innovation laid the foundation for modern 3D printing by enabling the manufacture of physical objects directly from digital designs. From a technological perspective, the process of constructing a 3D model or

3D haptic physical model [4] is consistent with currently available technologies [5]. The process can be divided into the following three parts. (1) A virtual 3D model is built using CAD software. (2) A specialized program called a slicer converts the 3D model into code that controls a 3D printer. The slicer optimizes parameters such as height and width of the line, print speed, etc. (3) Finally, code data are uploaded to the printer for printing.

The 3D-printing method not only efficiently produces plastic and metal objects. It can also be used with other materials that can be stored, extruded with precision, and fused with previous layers before solidifying under normal room conditions [6]. Example materials include food and other biomaterials [7–9]. Photopolymer materials can be 3D printed based on the principle of UV light hardening. This method is called stereolithography [10].

Concrete structures [11–13] are another example of recent advancements in 3D printing. Ceramic raw materials such as silicates, cements,

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: adam.boleslavsky@vsb.cz (A. Boleslavský).

or refractories can also be 3D printed [14]. Direct Ink Writing (DIW), a technology for printing pastes that harden over time, is commonly used to 3D print these materials [15]. DIW is also referred to as fused deposition modeling [16] or fused filament fabrication [17].

The manufacture of ceramics is undoubtedly challenging, both in terms of energy and raw material handling [18]. 3D-printing technology can help to mitigate some of this challenge. Generally, ceramic raw materials can be classified according to chemical composition into oxide ceramics such as Al_2O_3 , ZrO_2 , TiO_2 , ZnO , and SiO_2 and non-oxide ceramics such as carbides (SiC , B_4C , TiC , ZrC), nitrides (Si_3N_4 , AlN), titanates, phosphates, aluminates, and mixtures of ceramic materials (Al_2O_3 - ZrO_2 , Al_2O_3 - GdAlO_3 , Al_2O_3 - GdAlO_3 - ZrO_2 , Al_2O_3 - YAG , Al_2O_3 - SiO_2 , Si_3N_4 - SiO_2) [18].

Traditional manufacturing technologies for ceramic parts include pressing, casting, extrusion, injection molding, gel casting, and tape castings. The raw materials may come with or without additives and binders [19]. Many of these technologies are limited by mold design parameters. The conventional molding processes that are currently available cannot be used to form shapes with complex geometries or interconnected holes [19].

Relatively new to the scene, ceramic additive manufacturing via 3D printing has developed to include a wide range of ceramic materials using different molding or forming technologies. Compared to standard manufacturing methods, ceramic additive manufacturing presents new ceramic material possibilities. 3D printing can shape more complex geometries. Moreover, 3D printing can also print powders and slurries. Both compact and porous parts and macroporous lattice structures can be prepared [20–22]. 3D printers can also be used to extrude different ceramic and waste materials mixtures. Aluminosilicate and zirconium dioxide clays [23–25], bioceramics [26,27], composite or nanocomposite materials [28,29], function ceramics [30], geopolymers [31], and concrete [32,33] can all be 3D printed as a general rule.

Thanks to modern technologies in materials science and computer control a relatively large number of new technologies have been developed to 3D print raw ceramic materials whether in suspension, as a powder, or as a bulk material. 3D printing from suspensions involves liquid or semi-liquid materials in which fine ceramic particles are dispersed. For this type of additive technology, methods such as photopolymerization, inkjet printing, and extrusion are used. A good overview of the distribution of these technologies is also presented in these studies [21,34].

Currently, ceramic components are printed using many modern technologies such as selective laser sintering [35–37], stereolithography [38,39], binder jetting [40], material extrusion [41], and material jetting [42,43]. Particle size plays an important role. For binder jetting, particles should be smaller than $10\ \mu\text{m}$ to limit surface roughness, high porosity, and poor densification during sintering [19]. Size particles $<20\ \mu\text{m}$ are preferable for the robocasting technique to achieve better flow during the extrusion and sintering processes.

Direct ink writing was developed by Cesarani et al. at Sandia National Laboratories in 1997 to print ceramic pastes. This technique is easy, adaptable, and inexpensive and appropriate for a variety of raw materials such as monolithic or composite ceramic materials, polymers, and alloys [19,44,45]. As stated by the authors of [37], most scientific publications have focused on the DIW of advanced ceramic materials based on ZrO_2 and Al_2O_3 as well as on non-oxides. Few authors have researched the printing of traditional clays.

The principle of the DIW method is extrusion. The raw material, a non-Newtonian viscous suspension with rheological properties containing both a liquid and a solid phase, is printed at room temperature. The advantage of ceramic materials with viscoelastic behavior is that they retain their original shape even as additional layers are applied [46,47]. The final properties of the fired ceramic component are determined by viscosity, density, granulometry, shape and diameter of the nozzle, drying, and sintering. Compared to other relevant manufacturing

Table 1
Chemical composition of ceramic materials tested by XRF analysis.

Oxides (wt. %)							
Na_2O	MgO	Al_2O_3	SiO_2	P_2O_5	Fe_2O_3	K_2O	CaO
0,37	0,4	28,9	54,3	0,09	2,6	3,4	0,4
SO_3	TiO_2	V_2O_5	MnO	SrO	ZrO_2	Cl	LOI
0,27	1,4	0,05	0,01	0,01	0,05	<0,001	1,47

methods, DIW is economical and timesaving, and it results in minimum defects [48].

In study [49], the authors listed several companies active in the field of ceramic 3D printing. This shows the connection between academic research and industrial innovation. In addition, the 3D printed ceramics market shows an annual growth rate of more than 4%. The market is expected to reach \$3.6 billion by 2030 [50].

In this work, ceramic clay was 3D-print molded using the DIW method. Comparison samples were also prepared using cast molding. As part of the experiment, a detailed print optimization study was performed, including a description of the entire printing system, calibration, and optimization of printing parameters. The parameters of interest were compressive strength, bulk density, porosity, and the structure of the tested samples. Compared to other literature, this experiment describes several problems and reveals the deficiencies in 3D printing of the ceramic raw materials via results analysis. Observed deficiencies are described, and the paper offers solution ideas and suggests ways to improve the 3D-print molding process and the final 3D printed part.

2. Experimental part

The following paragraphs describe the materials tested and the equipment used to carry out this research work. The 3D-printing methodology is also described. Calibrations needed to achieve the results are also outlined. This section concludes by describing the fabrication of the test samples.

2.1. Description of the material

This raw ceramic material used to mold the test samples is a commercial product called chamotte clay. It is produced by Pavek s.r.o. (Czech Republic). From the manufacturer, the water content of the material may be different for each batch. For this material, the most common value is 22% water content. This should be increased by adding and mixing water up to 31%. This mix meets the requirements for printing on the equipment used. Specifically, the requirements for smooth movement of the material through the printing system, printing to the desired heights and consistency of the print line shape. The recommended firing temperature is between 980 and 1250 °C. Firing temperature influences the color of the ceramic, which becomes a light cream. X-ray fluorescence was used to determine the chemical composition of the molded clay. See Table 1. The iron oxide (5.44-9.89 wt%) results in dark red coloration after firing at high temperature [51]. The significant amount of Na_2O and K_2O content in the sample reflects the presence of feldspars. These are responsible for the formation of the amorphous phase, which improves the sintering process and lowers the required firing temperature. The high measured percentage of K_2O (3.37 wt%) comes from the mineral illite present in the clay [52]. The powdered clay had a relatively low Loss On Ignition (LOI) of 1.47 wt%. The LOI calculation reveals the amount of organic matter that was in the sample.

Figs. 1 and 2 show the mineralogical composition of ceramic clay detected by X-ray Diffraction (XRD) phase analysis using the powder method (XRPD). Quartz is shown as the main crystalline phase (SiO_2), and mullite ($3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$) as the second phase. The main quartz peak

Fig. 1. XRPD diffractogram of ceramic material before firing.

Fig. 2. XRPD diffractograms of ceramic material after firing up 1060 °C.

is in the range of 30–32 ° 2θ. The mullite phase frequently appears in the record. Crystalline mullite is the most common phase in silicate materials. It is a high-temperature ceramic phase that forms in the Al₂O₃-SiO₂ system.

Crystalline mullite is the most common phase in ceramic materials. It forms when kaolin is heated to a high temperature. Additionally, silica oxide and a silicon-rich liquid phase are also formed. Mullite has low thermal expansion, chemical resistance, and good resistance to

Table 2
Rheological parameters of the mixture (MA).

Mixture	CP of $G' = G''$ (kPa)	CP of τ (Pa)	LVR $\tan(\delta)$	LVR τ (Pa)
MA	42.62	2581	0.37	489.7

thermal shock [53,54]. Potassium mica as dehydroxylated muscovite is the next most prominent phase. Water is released at temperatures above 850 °C and the feldspars phase as albite ($\text{NaAlSi}_3\text{O}_8$). The presence of quartz and muscovite proves that the mixture will have good plastic properties and good binding capacity for hydroxyl or water molecules. The mixture is also suitable for 3D printing [55–57].

Shear-thinning behavior is crucial for efficient Direct Ink Writing (DIW) 3D printing of ceramics, which allows easy extrusion by reducing viscosity as shear stress increases [58]. The G' (storage modulus) and G'' (loss modulus) play an important role — their equality indicates the initiation of flow. Inappropriate flow stress can lead to either difficult extrusion (high) or spontaneous flow (low) [59].

Rheological measurements were performed using a rotational rheometer Thermo Haake MARS iQ Air at a temperature of 23 °C with parallel plates (\varnothing 25 mm, gap = 2 mm). Shear-thinning behavior was investigated using the Rotation Ramp test in Control Rate mode with a shear rate range from 0.0026 to 120 s^{-1} . The oscillatory Amplitude Sweep test ($f = 1$ Hz, $\tau = 1$ –5000 Pa) was used to determine the elastic modulus G' and the loss modulus G'' , enabling the observation of changes in the viscoelastic properties of the material. This test also allowed the identification of the linear viscoelastic region (LVR) boundary and the critical point $G' = G''$, which marks the transition from elastic to viscous behavior. Furthermore, the value of the loss tangent $\tan \delta$ (G''/G') was determined, which defines the ratio of the viscous and elastic components. This ratio, G''/G' , allows comparison of whether the material behaves more viscously or elastically. If $\tan \delta < 1$, elastic behavior dominates; if $\tan \delta > 1$, viscous behavior dominates; and if $\tan \delta = 1$, it represents the transition between elastic and viscous behavior.

The correct ratio of these components is key to controlling flow during 3D printing — if the material is too fluid, layers are prone to flowing, while if the material is too solid, irregular extrusion may occur. The results of these values allow print parameters to be optimized, including extrusion speed and layer setting time.

The results from the Rotation Ramp and Amplitude Sweep measurements are presented in Fig. 3. The specific values of Crossover Points (CP) for $G' = G''$, expressed in kPa and τ , Pa, are listed in Table 2. Additionally, the values for the End of LVR for τ , Pa, and the Damping Factor $\tan(\delta)$ are also included. Rheological measurements from the Rotation Ramp test in Control Rate mode confirmed the shear-thinning behavior of the ceramic paste used for 3D printing. The results from the Amplitude Sweep test validate the significance of the gel point ($G' = G'' \geq 10^3$ Pa) for achieving printability of 3D ceramic structures, as stated in the study [60]. The attainment of this crossover point is crucial for optimizing the composition of ceramic pastes, aligning with previously published criteria.

The measurements confirm that the paste exhibits rheofluidity, as shear-thinning behavior is observed — when higher shear stress is applied, the paste structure breaks down and begins to flow. This property is desirable for DIW 3D printing, as the paste must remain sufficiently solid at rest ($G' > G''$) while flowing easily when force is applied during extrusion.

For the estimation of the shear rate range at the nozzle, Eq. (1) [61] was used:

$$\dot{\gamma} = \frac{Q}{\pi r^3} \cdot \frac{3n+1}{n} (\text{s}^{-1}) \quad (1)$$

where $\dot{\gamma}$ is the shear rate (s^{-1}); Q is the volumetric flow rate ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$); r is the nozzle radius (m); and n is the flow behavior index (–).

Applying the Power-Law model to the measured viscosity data Fig. 3a, the flow behavior index was determined to be $n = 0.2483$. The volumetric flow rate Q was calculated as the product of the cross-sectional area of a single printed layer and the movement speed of the printhead. The nozzle radius was $r = 2$ mm. For a layer width of 4.5 mm, the shear rate was calculated as 75.5 s^{-1} , and for a layer width of 5.5 mm, as 92.5 s^{-1} .

2.2. 3D printing

A Make-R type printer modification for fused deposition modeling was adapted by the authors of [62] to print clay using the DIW method. Repetier Host software was used to configure the printing process. The following printers were used:

- a 3D-Bioplotter by EnvisionTEC with a 0.26 to 1.27 mm nozzle diameter, pneumatic pressure of 0.01–0.5 MPa, and speeds from 6 to 25 mm/s;
- a Techcon (Cypress CA, USA) adhesive dispensing system repurposed for clay extrusion featuring a 6-axis robotic arm (IRB 120, ABB, Switzerland), \varnothing 0.51–3 mm nozzles with pneumatic pressures ranging from 0.14–0.69 MPa, and speeds from 1 to 80 mm/s [37]; and
- a Delta Wasp 2040 3D with liquid deposition modeling, three nozzle sizes (1, 2, and 3 mm), and an air compression pump (0.4 and 0.6 MPa optimum pressure) and tank with a mechanical screw extruder [57].

Clay samples were also printed using a 3D Potter 7 pottery printer with a circular nozzle of \varnothing 5mm [63]. The mentioned printers are examples of printers with settings and equipment for DIW printing.

Fig. 4 illustrates the in-house-developed printer system used to DIW print the chamotte clay. The printer shown in Fig. 4(a) is based on the Tronxy X5SA model, which was originally designed for printing various plastic materials. A CoreXY printer was modified to print ceramic materials, utilizing equipment already available in existing inventory. The modification was designed to withstand the substantial loads generated during ceramic printing. Additionally, safeguards were implemented to prevent contamination from dirt and water. The decision to modify existing equipment for the purpose of printing ceramic materials proved to be more cost-effective. The results demonstrate that this choice was also successful from a technological standpoint. The printing process begins by filling the almost 4 l steel cylinder cartridge. It is necessary to ensure the elimination of air in the system. For this reason, a screw feeder is used for loading the cartridge. In this process, the material is manually loaded to the feeder and it mixes, compresses, and moves material into the cylindrical cartridge. This method is significantly more effective than manual filling, which can trap air within the material. To remove any residual air from the system, the extruder is equipped with venting holes in the section above the screw. This is a standard feature in commercial extruders. Once filled the ends of the cartridge are sealed by a piston and threaded lids. The compressor pressurizes the piston, which then pushes the raw material through a hole on the opposite end and through a tube connected to the extruder. The cartridge is suspended above the printer on a pulley system, with the compressor positioned nearby. The new extruder designed for this experiment (Fig. 4(b)) was made specifically for the ceramic raw material.

Development of the extruder was inspired by several studies on printing ceramic raw materials [64–66]. It accepts easily changeable plastic nozzles of 2, 4, 5, 8 and 10 mm diameter. Ceramic material is fed into the extruder from the side, and the extrusion itself is carried out utilizing a screw.

The described procedures and guides for 3D printing have been based on existing methodologies developed by other authors, particularly those presented by Jonathan Keep, who has been involved in 3D printing of ceramic materials for a long time [67]. Other authors and

Fig. 3. (a) Shear-thinning behavior, (b) Storage and Loss modulus measurement.

Fig. 4. (a) current state of the printing equipment, (b) design of new extruder.

manufacturers also have their own procedures, which differ slightly. The procedure described here is suitable for the equipment and material used.

The first step, after preparation of the material, is to calibrate the printer according to the recommended procedures and guides that deal with the correct adjustment and calibration of a CoreXY printer. In this experiment, the print bed is the tile on which the sample is printed. Since the tile is replaceable, it can be moved with the printed product that can be left to dry outside of the printer. A new tile is then provided for the next print. The correct Z-axis offset must be set for each new tile. Dimensional error can be on the order of millimeters in the case of incorrect calibration, which is noticeable when printing with smaller nozzle diameters. A simple test is performed to check that the printer is set up correctly and that the tile used is flat enough for printing.

Fig. 5 shows a bed-leveling print, a set of nested squares centered on a tile bed. The widths of the extruded lines correspond to the precise distance of the nozzle from the surface of the bed. If they are equal, then the printer gantry is level and the tile is flat. If, however, the print happens to be wider somewhere, this indicates that the printer gantry must be leveled or the tile bed is not sufficiently flat. For this

experiment, the substrate was first set up using a large straight tile bed. The prints themselves were then printed on the smaller tile pads. The bed was leveled for each new tile.

The next step is to set the material flow to the desired print line profile. This is done by printing out a square shape and adjusting the flow. Three different results can occur when measuring dimensions, as shown in Fig. 6. In case (a), insufficient material was extruded. Material flow must be increased. Flow rate must be monitored and adjusted until the result looks like (b). If material flow exceeds the correct value, it accumulates between the lines and packs onto the nozzle as shown in (c).

If the flow rate is even higher, a situation can occur at low speeds where the layers are pushed sideways by the material, and the material is smoothed from above by the nozzle. See (Fig. 7). Although there is accumulation on the nozzle, it is not as bad as the case in Fig. 6 (c).

Fig. 8 demonstrates the overall workflow of the experimental print process. It begins by preparing the 3D CAD model, which must be designed or adjusted to be printable. Overlaps, details, and manufacturing methods in respect of the material must be considered [68–70]. The model is then uploaded to a slicer where print setup takes place and

Fig. 5. Image of calibration pad print.

G-code is generated. Before printing, the printer is calibrated to ensure accuracy. The material is prepared and loaded. Then, the printing line is calibrated. Afterwards, printing can begin. Printing must be monitored and flow adjusted as needed to compensate for variations in raw material consistency. This issue can be mitigated by careful material mixing and handling.

Printing multiple copies of the same item reveals defects, limitations, and relationships specific to the variability of the ceramic clay. Print settings affect appearance. Printer size determines the maximum size that can be printed. And small system changes lead to different print results. A relationship map was prepared to determine how a given system change would affect other areas within the 3D printing process. Fig. 9 illustrates these relationships.

Printer choice affects the accuracy of the print, the size of the layers, and therefore the quality of the print. Printer calibration improves print accuracy. Poor calibration will affect the print from the beginning, and for this reason, careful calibration is critical to the printing process. The equipment is also affected by the material being printed. The equipment must be able to store and precisely extrude the material as directed by the G-code. Equipment and printer dimensions affect slicer settings such as print dimensions and layer sizes.

Another example of a relationship can be the requirement for serial printing. This is directly influenced by the equipment and print quality requirements of the product. Here, it is mainly about the degree of automation. For example, if the bed is changed, refills and calibration are done automatically. This would be the ideal situation for serial printing. Otherwise, when a human is involved in the process (changing the print pad, refilling the material for each print, etc.), serialization is still possible but becomes more challenging. The print setup will also affect the seriality of the print, indirectly through the desired quality of the desired printout.

The relationship map shown in Fig. 9 is a simplification that can be developed in greater detail. The map makes it possible to better examine the methodology and calibration. It can also be used to improve the print device, as even these small improvements can have a big impact on the end result.

2.3. Sample preparation

To produce the test samples for this research, chamotte clay was shaped into 5 x 5 x 5 cm cubes using traditional cast molding and

by 3D-print molding. In its original raw form, the clay had 22% water content. This percentage was increased to 31% by adding 1 l of water to 10 kg of clay to achieve optimal consistency and facilitate the molding methods.

The cast-molded cubes were made by pouring the chamotte clay into a rubber mold. After pouring, the clay and mold were vibrated for four minutes. After 24 h, solidified clay cubes were demolded. Fig. 10 shows the cast-molded cubes. The 3D-print-molded cubes were printed onto unglazed ceramic tiles. Fig. 12 shows the 3D-print-molded cubes. The demolded cast cubes and 3D-print-molded cubes were then dried at 105 °C for 24 h. They were then fired at 1060 °C for 5 h with 1 h of maintaining the maximum temperature in an electric resistance furnace without sheet and without cooling.

To avoid clogging during the 3D-print molding process, the clay must be extruded at pressures greater than 0.6 MPa. Lower pressures are not sufficient to overcome the pressure loss in the system. At 0.8 MPa, clogging does not occur, and extrudability is ensured. The volume of clay that will be required is fed into the feed cartridge. With the 3D-print molding process, shortages or excesses of material are not significant issues. At 0.8 MPa and with a 4 mm diameter nozzle, a print speed of 15 mm/s was suitable. The distance between the nozzle and the printing bed was set to 4 mm. The same height was maintained for the other layers. Clay water content remained relatively constant. The flow of extruded clay was steady. It did not accumulate nor did it drop out. Assuming equal pressure, the ideal print speed would be lower for larger diameter nozzles and higher for smaller diameter nozzles. Water content also affects extrudability, so the system must be carefully calibrated to accommodate the specific print medium. Fig. 11 illustrates the print result for the 0.8 MPa, 15 mm/s, 4 mm nozzle setup for the 31% water chamotte clay. The photo was captured within 5 min after the print was completed. The print bead was 4 mm thick and 4.5 to 5.5 mm wide. This corresponds to a setting of 5 mm in the slicer.

When the layers are laid side by side, they overlap. This deforms the clay material, which serves to flatten and align the bead and connect it to adjacent lines. Refer back to Fig. 6 (b). The chamotte clay material can slump under some conditions [71]. The diameter of the nozzle and the height of the print plays a role as does whether or not the print is single-walled, multi-walled, or has supports. Print speed also affects slumping. If the material is fed too fast, previous layers are flattened by the material flow. The cubes printed for this experiment were single-walled, the beads were of average height, and the nozzle diameter was 4 mm. Because, each bead was supported by adjacent lines and layers, slumping was minimal and not visible during printing. After printing, however, during the initial drying process, some slumping occurred.

Twelve of the 3D-print-molded cubes are shown in Fig. 12. Fig. 12(a) and b show the top and bottom of the cubes after initial drying. Figs. 12(c) and 12(d) show the tops and bottoms after firing. The tops (last printed layer) are relatively smooth (12(a) and 12(c)). On the other hand, each bead remained distinct on the bottom, which was in contact with the ceramic tile during extrusion (12(b) and 12(d)). The gaps between layers are relatively large. These gaps may be due to the choice of print bed surface or poor setup of the first layer. Figs. 12(b) and 12(d) show that firing did not affect these gaps.

Despite the effort to choose a print pad with low water absorption, because the tile used was unglazed, excess absorption probably resulted in the first layer bead gaps. Since firing did not affect these gaps, and because they only occur on the first layer, it is likely that they are the result of excess absorption of water into the print pad.

A lower quality glazed tile was chosen as the printing bed. The tile was chosen to avoid rapid water drainage, which when it occurs, creates cracks. Glass was not chosen as the experience with printing this material on glass is that the material does not hold in place and slides across the glass, ruining the print at the very beginning.

Fig. 13 shows a side view of the 3D printed cubes. Here you can see the deflection of the sample, which is completely negligible due to

Fig. 6. Print line profile settings.

Fig. 7. The case of high material flow and low printing speed.

Fig. 8. Printing phases.

the setup. Picture A is after drying and picture B is after firing. Even during firing, the profile did not change during shrinkage.

A more detailed analysis was performed by the authors [72]. A condition is presented where the elastic behavior of the clay is characterized, which tends to have a relatively linear deformation slope. Another state is characterized by plastic deformation, which is manifested by an exponential increase in deformation until complete collapse. The test results presented here agree with the authors and suggest that these states lead to a reliable estimate of the mechanical dynamics that occur during printing. This approach can therefore form the basis for the development of a comprehensive design method for the entire printing operation.

Kruger et al. [73], define buildability as the ability of a material to retain its shape after several layers have been printed. Which is measured by counting the number of stable printed layers before collapse [74]. Nozzle diameter and print speed significantly affect the buildability of the 3D-print-molded mixture [75]. To avoid print failures caused by the weight loading of each layer, certain stress constraints must be satisfied. These authors used the model to avoid the rheological parameters of materials such as concrete, which is a thixotropic material.

Therefore, a 3D-print molded material is subject to plastic stress if the self-weight of the layer exceeds its static yield strength. As concrete gains strength over time, its static yield strength changes. To

Fig. 9. Relationships in the printing process.

Fig. 10. Test cubes prepared by casting.

Fig. 11. Extruded line and its application to 3D-print-molded parts.

support the buildability of the optimized design, the geometric overlap of adjacent layers must be appropriately determined. This is especially important for structures with large curvatures or large overhangs. Lack of overlap may be one reason why the lowest layer has shifted outward in some experiments [76]. In article [77], print speed for the first layer was set to 50% for better adhesion to the print bed. In this case, cylindrical shapes with a diameter of 8 mm and a height of 4 mm were extruded.

3. Results and discussion

The following paragraphs describe the test results and how the test cubes were evaluated. Key parameters of interest include shrinkage and compressive strength. Test samples were also cut in half and analyzed, which helped to better reveal some defects and led to more discussion.

Bulk density BD is mass per unit volume. For the sample cube evaluated, this is influenced by the presence of cavities and pores.

Bulk density was determined by weighing the samples and dividing by measured volume. Bulk density was determined as part of absorption measurement.

Saturated cubes were weighed on hydrostatically balanced scales in water at a temperature of 23 ± 2 °C. Each newly formed water-saturated cube was suspended from an auxiliary structure, completely submerged, and positioned away from the walls of the container. The submerged weight m_2 was measured after removing air bubbles. Weight in air m_3 was measured after removing each cube from the water and wiping off the surface moisture with a damp cloth. ρ_{liq} is the density of the liquid in which the samples was immersed during the measurement. In our case it is water. Therefore, ρ_{liq} is equal to $998,2 \text{ kg/m}^3$. After oven drying, another measurement was made to determine the weight of the dry cube m_1 . Eq. (2) were used to calculate bulk density of the cubes. (EN 771-1, EN 72 2603)

$$BD = \frac{m_1}{m_3 - m_2} \cdot \rho_{\text{liq}} \left(\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3} \right) \quad (2)$$

Fig. 12. Cubes prepared by 3D-print molding (a) top of cubes after drying (b) bottom of cubes after drying (c) top of cubes after firing (d) bottom of cubes after firing.

where ρ_{liq} is the density of the liquid in which the samples were immersed during the measurement ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$); m_1 is dry sample weight (kg); m_2 is mass of the sample saturated with liquid in water (kg) and m_3 is mass of the liquid-saturated sample in air (kg).

Absorption (EN 771-1) is the ability of the fired ceramic material to absorb liquid. It was determined in percentage as the ratio of the weight of water absorbed by the test cube to the weight of the dried cube (absolute mass absorption). The weighed and dried cubes were placed in the container so that they did not touch the sides or each other. Water was then poured into the container until they were completely submerged. The water was then heated to the boiling point and held there for 2 h. As it evaporated away, more water was continually added to ensure the cubes remained submerged. After boiling, the cubes were allowed to air cool to ambient temperature. They were then surface dried and weighed. The absorbance WA , (3) in % is expressed as follows.

$$WA = \frac{m_4 - m_5}{m_5} \cdot 100(\%) \quad (3)$$

where m_4 is weight of the sample after the absorption test (kg) and m_5 is weight of the dried sample (kg)

Apparent porosity AP is the ratio of the volume of open pores and voids of a cube to its total volume including all pores and voids. The true porosity is the ratio of the volume of open and closed pores and cavities of the sample to its total volume including all pores and cavities. The calculation is performed according to Eq. (4).

$$AP = \frac{m_3 - m_1}{m_3 - m_2} \cdot 100(\%) \quad (4)$$

The compressive strength CS of each sample was measured using a hydraulic press (EN 772-1, EN 72 2605). Each cube was placed on the lower pressure plate of the press and carefully loaded so that the upper pressure plate, equipped with a ball joint, sits flush with and covers the entire surface of the cube. Compressive load is applied and increased continuously until the sample breaks. The compressive strength of the sample in MPa was calculated using Eq. (5).

$$CS = \frac{F}{S} (\text{Pa}) \quad (5)$$

Fig. 13. Side view of the 3D printed cubes (a) after drying, (b) after firing.

where F is the highest load in Newtons at the cube breaking point, and S is the compression area in mm^2 calculated from the measured dimensions of the original sample.

The chamotte clay was characterized by X-ray diffraction, X-ray fluorescence, and determined mechanical properties. The chemical composition of the sample in the powdered state was determined by a method of energy-dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy on the SPECTRO XEPOS (Spectro Analytical Instruments, Kleve, Germany). The mineralogical composition of samples was evaluated using X-ray diffraction analysis on the X-ray diffractometer MiniFlex 600 equipped 270 with Co tube and D/teX Ultra detector. The XRD patterns were recorded in $5\text{--}90^\circ$ 2θ with a scanning rate of $5^\circ \times \text{min}$ (Rigaku, Japan). The thermal treatment of the samples was performed using an LAC laboratory furnace (LAC s.r.o.). Compressive strength was measured on an LLB1 hydraulic press (Brio Hranice s.r.o., Hranice, Czech Republic) according to the standard [78].

In total, each 3D printed cube was measured three times. It was first measured immediately after printing. Each cube and the pad it was printed on was carefully transferred to a rotating platform. See Fig. 14(a). This platform was connected to a computer as well as the Photoneo PhoXi 3D Scanner M (Photoneo s.r.o.). Once the scanner was loaded and calibrated test samples were scanned to an accuracy of 0.05 mm. The scanning settings were every 10° , resulting in 36 images for each cube. This setting was sufficient to render the details of the scanned samples. Fig. 14(b) shows the results of a scan after filtering. Fig. 14(c) shows a 3D-CAD model generated from the same scan. The model is then saved as a stereolithography file (STL), which then must be further processed.

Since the pad that each cube was printed on also shows up on the scan, it had to be removed. This was done in the Prusa slicer software (Fig. 14(d)). Since the pad is planar, the slicer was able to remove it without removing any material from the test cube.

Table 3 summarizes the average shrinkage values measured for the 3D-print-molded cubes. The measurements were taken to determine average shrinkage after drying and firing. During firing, ceramic raw materials shrink. The sintering process increases density. For 3D-print-molded objects, shrinking and densification is uneven due to the layering involved in printing. This can be a complication when printing complex geometric components [79].

Drying caused the test cubes to shrink by 6.95% on average in the X axis and 7.25% in the Y axis. In the Z axis, shrinkage was more prominent than in the X and Y axes due to the gravitational downward displacement of the material. Average shrinkage due to drying in the Z axis was 11.09%. After firing, an additional shrinkage

Table 3

Average shrinkage and water loss data.

Parameter	Value (%)
Average Shrinkage	
X -axis shrinkage after drying	-6.95
X -axis shrinkage after firing	-5.45
Y -axis shrinkage after drying	-7.25
Y -axis shrinkage after firing	-5.11
Z -axis shrinkage after drying	-11.09
Z -axis shrinkage after firing	-6.84
Total Shrinkage (in total)	
X -axis	-11.61
Y -axis	-11.49
Z -axis	-17.26
Average Water Loss	
Water loss after drying	-24.99
Water loss after firing	-8.08
Total average water content	-31.06

Table 4

Average water content loss values for 3D printed samples.

Average water loss		
After drying	24,99	%
After firing	8,08	%
In total	31,06	%

5.32% was observed in the X axis and 5.16% in the Y axis. Again, under the same forces, larger average shrinkage was recorded in the Z axis. It was 6.90%. Total shrinkage from the raw 3D-print molded cube to the fired ceramic cube was 11.90%, 12.04%, and 17.2% for X , Y , and Z -axes, respectively. This represents a total volumetric shrinkage of 36%.

Table 4 summarizes the 3D-print-molded cube weight measurements. The percentage loss and the overall average water content of the sample were then calculated from the weights. The average water loss from 3D-print-molding to drying is 24.99%. After firing, there was an additional 8.08% average water weight loss. The overall average water loss from print to firing was 31.06%. This 31.06% corresponds to the initial 31.06% water content for the chamotte clay.

Several methods can be used to characterize silicate materials. In this paper, the authors focus on basic laboratory tests, which provide important information about the tested ceramic material. The main indicators of quality for ceramic products and materials are compressive strength, bulk density, water absorption, and apparent porosity. Table 5 summarizes the average result measured for each of these parameters for the ceramic cubes produced using both 3D-print molding and cast molding.

Fig. 14. The process of measuring and scanning samples — (a) the process of taking images on a rotary table using a Photoneo camera, (b) removing redundant and unnecessary objects, (c) unifying images and building a 3D model of the scanned object, and (d) cutting the tile off the 3D model and obtaining a transformed 3D model of the cube.

Table 5
Parameters of tested samples.

Method of preparing the samples	Compressing strength (MPa)	Bulk density BD (g.cm ⁻³)	Apparent porosity (%) AP	Water absorption (%) A
Sample by casting	30.1	2.1	12.1	5.7
Sample by printing	31.4	2.0	15.1	7.4

The properties of both were compared. Since the cubes are heterogeneous, their granulometry, the way they have been prepared, and how they are dried and fired all play an important role in the ultimate ceramic properties. The way these cubes were fired is different than the way advanced ceramics, which use finer particles in the raw materials, are fired. 3D-print-molded parts are generally lower in density, which leads to fired parts that are also lower in density [80].

The average compressive strength measured for the 3D-print-molded cubes was ~31 MPa. Comparable numbers for clays with different W/C ratios achieved between 30–45 MPa. These test samples were 20 mm and 10 mm diameter cylinders printed with 1-, 1.6-, and 3-mm nozzle diameters and fired at 1100 °C [62]. Compressive strength values for cast-molded samples are typically similar. The apparent porosity of the 3D-print-molded cubes was ~14%, and absorbance was ~7%. The surface roughness and porosity of the 3D-print-molded ceramic cubes significantly affects these parameters. The cast-molded cubes exhibited lower apparent porosity and at the same time lower water absorption. Bulk density was comparable for both.

Fig. 15 shows cubes before and after the compressive-strength test. Cracking was vertical along the entire length of the sample. The 3D-print-molded ceramic cube seems to have experienced more damage.

The main indicators of quality for ceramic products and materials are compressive strength, bulk density, water absorption, and apparent porosity. The samples were tested according by Czech norm ČSN EN 993(726020): Methods of test for dense shaped refractory products — Part 1: Determination of bulk density, apparent porosity and true porosity and Part 5: Determination of crushing strength. Addition of Standard Deviations. The all values are average from 5 samples. As presented in Table 5, the average PTL for the initial five samples was 31.4 MPa (± 4 MPa). The authors supplemented the dataset with an additional extra 9 printed samples. In this case, the average CS for all 14 samples was 33.15 MPa (± 3 MPa). As expected, with a larger sample size, the standard deviation decreases. The PTL results are available in the Supplementary Materials.

Fig. 16 shows how the cast-molded and 3D-print-molded ceramic cubes fractured in compressive-strength testing. The difference in brittleness is immediately apparent. The more brittle cast-molded and fired cube (a) has more and sharper broken edges. Closed pores of different sizes and shapes are visible. The less brittle 3D-print-molded and fired cube (b) presents a more compact fracture surface. Here, too, closed micropores are visible, corresponding to the ends of both lines. However, these pores are much smaller than in the cast-molded cube.

Fig. 15. Compressive strength testing of cubes — (a) original cast-molded and fired ceramic cube before testing and (b) after testing — (c) 3D-print-molded and fired ceramic cube before testing and (d) after testing.

Fig. 16. Fragments of ceramic cubes broken during compressive-strength testing — (a) cast-molded and fired and (b) 3D-print-molded and fired.

Fig. 17 shows the dried samples. The samples are after cutting: (A) casting samples and (B) print samples. There are no visible cracks in any of the samples. In figure A, only three visible open pores and traces of disc cutting are present. In Figure B, open micropores can be seen at the ends of the two intersecting lines forming a triangle, representing the pores between the layers. The sharp edges are unfortunately the

result of disc cutting, but no visible cracks are present. Unfortunately, the printing lines are not visible in Figure B. During the cutting process, the individual layers in the sample were smoothed. There is no evidence of cracks in either sample.

Compressive strength is affected by porosity. It depends on the quantity, size, and distribution of the internal pores. Porous ceramic

Fig. 17. Cross section of dried samples (a) Casting sample after drying, (b) 3D printed sample after drying.

has been categorized as (1) having <50 nm/macro-porosity, (2) having $2\text{ nm} < d < 50\text{ nm}$ /meso-porosity, and (3) having $d < 2\text{ nm}$ /micro-porosity [80].

The nature of the porosity resulting from each manufacturing process depends on several particular factors. For instance, the porosity resulting from cast-molding and firing depends strongly on the porosity of the original clay matrix. The porosity from 3D-print-molding and firing is defined by the parameters of the printing process and the limitations of the specific printing technology [80]. Internal defects result in poor overall mechanical properties. Cracks also severely affect the mechanical properties of ceramic parts and pose the biggest obstacle to advancing the practical application of finished products. In some ceramics, pores less than $5\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ in size can also reduce mechanical strength [48].

For the cubes tested here, surface porosity was minimal, but the interior did contain some cracking and closed pores. Figs. 18 and 19 reveal interior details for both a cast-molded and fired cube and a 3D-print-molded and fired cube. Fig. 18(b) shows a few interior cracks and pores present in a bisected cast-molded ceramic cube. The larger crack shown is 3 cm long with an average width of $370\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 18(a)). Fig. 18(c) shows a larger image of two of the pores revealing both their shape and size. Fig. 19(b) and (c) shows a thin crack of length 2,5 mm with an average width of $100\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ in a bisected 3D-print-molded ceramic cube. The surfaces are compact and without defect, however, atypical microscopic porosity is evident. Open micropores were also visible that corresponded to the extremities of two lines that formed a triangle, e.g., interline 3D printing porosity. Fig. 16c reveals the detail and shape of two interior pores.

Defects of different lengths and morphologies result when 3D-print molding ceramic clays. An example is the interior voids brought about by discontinuities in extrusion lines due to incorrect extrusion speed or occasional nozzle clogging. Bubbles can also form as the ceramic clays are being extruded through a nozzle. This may result in the formation of oval pores, which may be closed and interconnected by intergranular porosity. Pores slightly larger than the intergranular spaces may arise from density heterogeneities in the feed materials, and cracks may then form during drying, sintering, and cooling of the 3D-print-molded ceramic.

Fig. 20 shows a surface of both a bisected cast-molded and fired and 3D-print-molded and fired ceramic cube. In the 3D-print-molded ceramic (Fig. 20(b)), the layers formed by individual lines have produced a symmetrical grid-like structure. The center of the lines is lighter in color than the edges. This is probably caused by water being forced out of the material to the surface of the line as it is extruded. There is less water content in the interior of each and more water content at its surface causing the interior to be lighter in weight. The cast-molded

cube does not have this grid irregularity. It does, however, still show areas of lighter and darker color, which reflect how thoroughly the clay and water were mixed prior to casting.

A crack is visible in both of the bisected cube surfaces shown in Fig. 20. Near the cube center in both cases, these cracks are probably a product of the drying process. In the 3D-print-molded ceramic cube, the crack has formed between extrusion lines in the darker colored region where, as previously noted, water concentration was highest. The cast-molded and fired cube also cracked, and the crack also formed in the darker higher-water-content region.

Bubbles that form during extrusion can ruin a 3D-print-molded part. There were no visible bubbles in the 3D-print molded cubes prepared for this study, but bubbles were present in the cast-molded cubes. Larger bubbles in the ceramic clay, most likely the result of the mixing process, can develop into cracks as the clay dries. Fig. 21 is a photo of the surface of a 3D-print-molded shard broken during compressive-strength testing. The left edge of the shard in the photo corresponds to a vertical edge of the unbroken cube. Small triangular-shaped pores are visible near this edge. This can be caused by insufficient material flow, but is probably due to air captured as the lines were extruded around the corner.

The first two layers of the 3D-print-molded cubes were prone to cracking. The bottom region of Fig. 21 photo. This cracking was probably caused by loss of water from the first clay layer as it is absorbed into the ceramic tile the clay is being extruded on. While not overly absorbent, the first layer does lose some water to the tile. The fact that the structure here was already disturbed by trapped air may have caused small cracks to form in the second layer during drying that grew during firing. This cracking can also propagate along the grid lines prevalent in 3D-print-molded parts.

Removing the bottom layers before drying is one possible solution to this problem. The first layer could be extruded closer to the bed to avoid trapping air, and the resulting elephant foot affected layers could then be cut away.

The authors of [62] tested 4 types of base layers. The best adhesion result was achieved with an unglazed ceramic tile, due to the rough surface and absorbency of the tiles. Glazed tile, due to its very smooth and impermeable surface, was less absorbent but offered little adhesion. A paper bed also worked, but it was deformed by the water it absorbed. Aluminum sheet turned out to be an unsuitable bed material. The strong adhesion of the extruded material to the aluminum did not allow the clay material to shrink as it dried, which resulted in cracking. [81].

Further work could also be done to optimize the printer bed material to minimize absorption while still allowing shrinkage, or another drying method that is less likely to result in cracking could be used.

Fig. 18. Detail defects of cast-molded and fired cube — (a) the width of the larger interior crack shown in the middle photo, (b) interior cracks and pores, and (c) the size and shape of two of the pores shown in the middle photo.

Fig. 19. Detail of defects of 3D-print-molded and fired cube — (a) the width of the interior crack shown in the middle photo, (b) an interior crack and pores, and (c) the size and shape of pores after compressive-strength testing.

Fig. 20. Section through the ceramic cubes produced by (a) cast molding and (b) 3D-print molding.

Fig. 21. Edge layer shear resulting from the compressive strength testing of a 3D-print-molded ceramic cube.

The 3D-print-molded and fired cube failed during compressive-strength testing along cracks that originated in and propagated from the first 2 layers. The bottom layer cracks helped to form regular fractures across the cube. Despite this failure mode, however, the 3D-print-molded and fired cube performed well. The good result can be linked to the regularity of the layers and the extruded layer-induced grid discussed previously. Preventing crack formation in the initial two layers during extrusion could potentially improve compressive strength.

4. Conclusions

The findings of this study provide valuable insight and new directions for advancing the 3D-print molding of ceramics. Using the direct ink writing method, this research explored the optimization of 3D-printing processes to enhance the mechanical and structural properties of manufactured ceramics parts. A comparative analysis of 3D-print-molded and cast-molded ceramic cubes revealed that 3D printing promises comparable, and in some cases superior, performance metrics.

Key outcomes include the demonstration of successful 3D-print-molding of the chamotte clay material to yield ceramic test cubes with 31.4 MPa compressive strength as compared to 30.4 MPa for the cast-molded ceramic cubes. Bulk density, porosity, and water absorption were also evaluated, showing that although the 3D-print-molded samples had slightly higher porosity (14.5%) and water absorption (7.1%) than samples prepared by cast-molding. Their mechanical performance remained competitive. Additionally, dimensional shrinkage during drying and firing was systematically measured, with observed total shrinkage of 36% or 11.9%, 12.04%, and 17.22% along the X, Y, and Z axes, respectively.

This research highlights the potential for further methodological improvements to enhance the properties of 3D-print-molded ceramics, enabling them to outperform traditionally cast-molded parts in both mechanical strength and material efficiency. Detailed cross-sectional analysis of the test cubes identified specific shortcomings in both compression cast molding and 3D-print molding, suggesting targeted areas for refinement. Addressing these challenges could lead to significant advancements that would enable 3D-print-molded ceramics and similar materials to achieve superior properties compared to conventional manufacturing methods.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Adam Boleslavský: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Hana Ovčáčková:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Milan Mihola:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation. **Aki Mikkola:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Michaela Topinková:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **Zdenko Bobovský:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This article was created as part of the project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004631 Materials and technologies for sustainable development within the Jan Amos Komenský Operational Program financed by the European Union and from the state budget of the Czech Republic.

This article was co-funded by the European Union under REFRESH (Research Excellence For REgion Sustainability and High-tech Industries) project number CZ.10.03.01/00/22_003/0000048 via the Operational Programme Just Transition and by specific research project SP2025/042, financed by the state budget of the Czech Republic.

doc. Ing. Jiří Rozbroj, Ph.D for the determination and evaluation of rheological properties for this experiment. VSB Technical University of Ostrava, Faculty of Mining and Geology, Department and Mining Engineering and Safety.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceram.2025.100797>.

Data availability

Data are available here: zenodo.org/records/14161699.

References

- [1] S.M. Fijul Kabir, Kavita Mathur, Abdel-Fattah M. Seyam, A critical review on 3D printed continuous fiber-reinforced composites: History, mechanism, materials and properties, *Compos. Struct.* (ISSN: 0263-8223) 232 (2020) 111476, <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2019.111476>.
- [2] Balaji Bharath Kumar Subbiah, Benefits and Challenges of Firm's Expansion to the European Market, Technical University of Liberec, Faculty of Economics, Liberec, 2022, Supervisor: Prof. Ing. Jan Kocourek, Ph.D. URL <https://dspace.tul.cz/handle/15240/173687>.
- [3] Carlos A. Gonzalez Lengua, History of rapid prototyping, in: Kanwal Majeed Farooqi (Ed.), *Rapid Prototyping in Cardiac Disease: 3D Printing the Heart*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, ISBN: 978-3-319-53523-4, 2017, pp. 3–7, https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-53523-4_1.
- [4] F. Rengier, et al., 3D printing based on imaging data: review of medical applications, *Int. J. Comput. Assist. Radiol. Surg.* (ISSN: 1861-6429) 5 (4) (2010) 335–341, <https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11548-010-0476-x>.
- [5] Xin Wang, et al., 3D printing of polymer matrix composites: A review and prospective, *Compos. Part B: Eng.* (ISSN: 1359-8368) 110 (2017) 442–458, <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2016.11.034>.
- [6] Anketa Jandyal, et al., 3D printing – A review of processes, materials and applications in industry 4.0, *Sustain. Oper. Comput.* (ISSN: 2666-4127) 3 (2022) 33–42, <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.susoc.2021.09.004>.
- [7] N. Nachal, et al., Applications of 3D printing in food processing, *Food Eng. Rev.* (ISSN: 1866-7929) 11 (3) (2019) 123–141, <https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s12393-019-09199-8>.

- [8] John Y. Zhang, et al., Advancements in 3D food printing: a comprehensive overview of properties and opportunities, *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr.* 62 (17) (2022) 4752–4768, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2021.1878103>, PMID: 33533641.
- [9] Sylvester Mantihal, Rovina Kobun, Boon-Beng Lee, 3D food printing of as the new way of preparing food: A review, *Int. J. Gastron. Food Sci.* (ISSN: 1878-450X) 22 (2020) 100260, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijgfs.2020.100260>.
- [10] J. Huang, Q. Qin, J. Wang, A review of stereolithography: Processes and systems, *Processes* 8 (9) (2020) 1138, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/pr8091138>.
- [11] M.A. Khan, Mix suitable for concrete 3D printing: A review, *Mater. Today: Proc.* (ISSN: 2214-7853) 32 (2020) 831–837, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2020.03.825>, 3rd International Conference on Innovative Technologies for Clean and Sustainable Development.
- [12] Shaodan Hou, et al., A review of 3D printed concrete: Performance requirements, testing measurements and mix design, *Constr. Build. Mater.* (ISSN: 0950-0618) 273 (2021) 121745, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2020.121745>.
- [13] Jianzhuang Xiao, et al., Large-scale 3D printing concrete technology: Current status and future opportunities, *Cem. Concr. Compos.* (ISSN: 0958-9465) 122 (2021) 104115, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2021.104115>.
- [14] Feng Zhang, et al., A review of 3D printed porous ceramics, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* (ISSN: 0955-2219) 42 (8) (2022) 3351–3373, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2022.02.039>.
- [15] M.A.S.R. Saadi, et al., Direct ink writing: A 3D printing technology for diverse materials, *Adv. Mater.* 34 (28) (2022) 2108855, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/adma.202108855>.
- [16] Omar A. Mohamed, Syed H. Masood, Jahar L. Bhowmik, Optimization of fused deposition modeling process parameters: a review of current research and future prospects, *Adv. Manuf.* (ISSN: 2195-3597) 3 (1) (2015) 42–53, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s40436-014-0097-7>.
- [17] Ans Al Rashid, Muammer Koç, Fused filament fabrication process: A review of numerical simulation techniques, *Polymers* (ISSN: 2073-4360) 13 (20) (2021) <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/polym13203534>.
- [18] Dylan D. Furszyfer Del Rio, et al., Decarbonizing the ceramics industry: A systematic and critical review of policy options, developments and sociotechnical systems, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* (ISSN: 1364-0321) 157 (2022) 112081, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112081>.
- [19] Aamir Shahzad, Ismail Lazoglu, Direct ink writing (DIW) of structural and functional ceramics: Recent achievements and future challenges, *Compos. Part B: Eng.* (ISSN: 1359-8368) 225 (2021) 109249, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2021.109249>.
- [20] Tingting Wang, Xuefeng Lu, Ao Wang, A review: 3D printing of microwave absorption ceramics, *Int. J. Appl. Ceram. Technol.* 17 (6) (2020) 2477–2491, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/ijac.13604>.
- [21] Zhangwei Chen, et al., 3D printing of ceramics: A review, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* (ISSN: 0955-2219) 39 (4) (2019) 661–687, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2018.11.013>.
- [22] Ya. Yu. Filippov, et al., Stereolithography 3D printed calcium pyrophosphate macroporous ceramics for bone grafting, *Open Ceram.* (ISSN: 2666-5395) 8 (2021) 100185, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.oceram.2021.100185>.
- [23] Alexander Wolf, Philipp Laurens Rosendahl, Ulrich Knaack, Additive manufacturing of clay and ceramic building components, *Autom. Constr.* (ISSN: 0926-5805) 133 (2022) 103956, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2021.103956>.
- [24] Vincenzo Gentile, et al., 3D-printed clay components with high surface area for passive indoor moisture buffering, *J. Build. Eng.* (ISSN: 2352-7102) 91 (2024) 109631, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.job.2024.109631>.
- [25] Javier Alonso Madrid, et al., 3D claying: 3D printing and recycling clay, *Crystals* (ISSN: 2073-4352) 13 (3) (2023) <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/cryst13030375>.
- [26] Yasi Chen, et al., Applications and progress of 3D printed bioceramic scaffolds in bone tissue repair and immune regulation, *Ceram. Int.* (ISSN: 0272-8842) 50 (23, Part A) (2024) 48891–48908, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2024.09.294>.
- [27] J. Roleček, et al., Bioceramic scaffolds fabrication: Indirect 3D printing combined with ice-templating vs. robocasting, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* (ISSN: 0955-2219) 39 (4) (2019) 1595–1602, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2018.12.006>.
- [28] René Wick-Joliat, Dirk Penner, Flexible interconnected ceramic parts 3D printed by two-component material extrusion with water-soluble support structures, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* (ISSN: 0955-2219) 43 (11) (2023) 4877–4884, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2023.03.069>.
- [29] Nestor Washington Solís Pinargote, et al., Direct ink writing technology (3D printing) of graphene-based ceramic nanocomposites: A review, *Nanomaterials* (ISSN: 2079-4991) 10 (7) (2020) <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/nano10071300>.
- [30] Yixuan Wang, Yanyan Bu, Xiangfu Wang, Advances in 3D printing of structural and functional ceramics: Technologies, properties, and applications, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* (ISSN: 0955-2219) 44 (14) (2024) 116653, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2024.05.075>.
- [31] Fatheali A. Shilar, et al., A review of 3D printing of geopolymer composites for structural and functional applications, *Constr. Build. Mater.* (ISSN: 0950-0618) 400 (2023) 132869, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2023.132869>.
- [32] C. Gosselin, et al., Large-scale 3D printing of ultra-high performance concrete – a new processing route for architects and builders, *Mater. Des.* (ISSN: 0264-1275) 100 (2016) 102–109, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2016.03.097>.
- [33] Ali Kazemian, et al., Cementitious materials for construction-scale 3D printing: Laboratory testing of fresh printing mixture, *Constr. Build. Mater.* (ISSN: 0950-0618) 145 (2017) 639–647, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2017.04.015>.
- [34] Sri Bharani Ghantasala, et al., Shrinkage and deformation of material extrusion 3D printed parts during sintering: Numerical simulation and experimental validation, *Acta Mater.* (ISSN: 1359-6454) 282 (2025) 120518, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2024.120518>.
- [35] Fen Chen, et al., Microstructure and mechanical properties of 3Y-TZP dental ceramics fabricated by selective laser sintering combined with cold isostatic pressing, *Int. J. Light. Mater. Manuf.* (ISSN: 2588-8404) 1 (4) (2018) 239–245, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijlmm.2018.09.002>.
- [36] Loïc Ferrage, Ghislaine Bertrand, Pascal Lenormand, Dense yttria-stabilized zirconia obtained by direct selective laser sintering, *Addit. Manuf.* (ISSN: 2214-8604) 21 (2018) 472–478, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2018.02.005>.
- [37] Shareen S.L. Chan, et al., 3D printing of clay for decorative architectural applications: Effect of solids volume fraction on rheology and printability, *Addit. Manuf.* (ISSN: 2214-8604) 35 (2020) 101335, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2020.101335>.
- [38] Li Wang, et al., Fabrication of highly translucent yttria-stabilized zirconia ceramics using stereolithography-based additive manufacturing, *Ceram. Int.* (ISSN: 0272-8842) 49 (11, Part A) (2023) 17174–17184, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2023.02.081>.
- [39] Qin Lian, et al., Accurate printing of a zirconia molar crown bridge using three-part auxiliary supports and ceramic mask projection stereolithography, *Ceram. Int.* (ISSN: 0272-8842) 45 (15) (2019) 18814–18822, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2019.06.111>.
- [40] Huoping Zhao, et al., Improving the properties of binder jetted ceramics via nanoparticle dispersion infiltration, *Ceram. Int.* (ISSN: 0272-8842) 48 (22) (2022) 33580–33587, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2022.07.302>.
- [41] Amir Hadian, et al., Material extrusion based additive manufacturing of large zirconia structures using filaments with ethylene vinyl acetate based binder composition, *Addit. Manuf.* (ISSN: 2214-8604) 47 (2021) 102227, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2021.102227>.
- [42] Zhongqi Zhu, et al., Additive manufacturing of thin electrolyte layers via inkjet printing of highly-stable ceramic inks, *J. Adv. Ceram.* (ISSN: 2227-8508) 10 (2) (2021) 279–290, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s40145-020-0439-9>.
- [43] E. Willems, et al., Additive manufacturing of zirconia ceramics by material jetting, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* (ISSN: 0955-2219) 41 (10) (2021) 5292–5306, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2021.04.018>.
- [44] Siqi Ma, et al., Direct ink writing of porous SiC ceramics with geopolymer as binder, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* (ISSN: 0955-2219) 42 (15) (2022) 6815–6826, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2022.08.004>.
- [45] K. Hartmann, et al., Robot-assisted shape deposition manufacturing, in: *Proceedings of the 1994 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, 1994, pp. 2890–2895 vol.4, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/ROBOT.1994.350900>.
- [46] Tobias Schlordt, et al., Robocasting of alumina hollow filament lattice structures, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* (ISSN: 0955-2219) 33 (15) (2013) 3243–3248, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2013.06.001>.
- [47] J.E. Smay, et al., Directed colloidal assembly of 3D periodic structures, *Adv. Mater.* 14 (18) (2002) 1279–1283, [http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/1521-4095\(20020916\)14:18<1279::AID-ADMA1279>3.0.CO;2-A](http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/1521-4095(20020916)14:18<1279::AID-ADMA1279>3.0.CO;2-A).
- [48] Emil Johansson, et al., Influence of resin composition on the defect formation in alumina manufactured by stereolithography, *Materials* (ISSN: 1996-1944) 10 (2) (2017) <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/ma10020138>.
- [49] Mohamed Abdelkader, et al., Ceramics 3D printing: A comprehensive overview and applications, with brief insights into industry and market, *Ceramics* (ISSN: 2571-6131) 7 (1) (2024) 68–85, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/ceramics7010066>.
- [50] Yongqin Zhao, et al., 3D printing of unsupported multi-scale and large-span ceramic via near-infrared assisted direct ink writing, *Nat. Commun.* (ISSN: 2041-1723) 14 (1) (2023) 2381, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-38082-8>.
- [51] Michele Dondi, Mariarosa Raimondo, Chiara Zanelli, Clays and bodies for ceramic tiles: Reappraisal and technological classification, *Appl. Clay Sci.* (ISSN: 0169-1317) 96 (2014) 91–109, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.clay.2014.01.013>, Clay Science & Technology (XV International Clay Conference).
- [52] Youssef Arkame, et al., Evaluation and application of moroccan clay materials in ceramic tiles: Composition and technological behavior, *Open Ceram.* (ISSN: 2666-5395) 18 (2024) 100591, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.oceram.2024.100591>.
- [53] H. Schneider, et al., Mullite precursor phases, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* (ISSN: 0955-2219) 11 (1) (1993) 87–94, [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0955-2219\(93\)90062-V](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0955-2219(93)90062-V).
- [54] Pallavi Suhasinee Behera, Sunipa Bhattacharyya, Effect of different alumina sources on phase formation and densification of single-phase mullite ceramic – reference clay alumina system, *Mater. Today Commun.* (ISSN: 2352-4928) 26 (2021) 101818, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.mtcomm.2020.101818>.
- [55] I.Z. Mukasa-Tebandeke, et al., The elemental, mineralogical, IR, DTA and XRD analyses characterized clays and clay minerals of central and eastern uganda, *Adv. Mater. Phys. Chem.* Vol.05No.02 (2015) 20, <http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/amc.2015.52010>.

- [56] F.R.S. Deer, R.A. Howie, J. Zussman, *An Introduction to the Rock-Forming Minerals*, Mineralogical Society of Great Britain and Ireland, ISBN: 9780903056274, 2013, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1180/DHZ>.
- [57] Arslan Yousaf, Ans Al Rashid, Muammer Koç, Parameter tuning for sustainable 3D printing(3DP) of clay structures, *J. Eng. Res.* (ISSN: 2307-1877) (2024) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jer.2024.05.027>.
- [58] Ria D. Corder, et al., Rheology of 3D printable ceramic suspensions: effects of non-adsorbing polymer on discontinuous shear thickening, *Soft Matter* 19 (2023) 882–891, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1039/D2SM01396G>.
- [59] Szymon Przybył a, et al., Optimization of ceramic paste composition for 3D printing via robocasting, *Materials* (ISSN: 1996-1944) 17 (18) (2024) <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/ma17184560>.
- [60] José Bonilla-Cruz, et al., 3D printable ceramic pastes design: Correlating rheology & printability, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* (ISSN: 0955-2219) 42 (13) (2022) 6033–6039, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2022.06.029>.
- [61] Daniel A. Rau, Christopher B. Williams, Michael J. Bortner, Rheology and printability: A survey of critical relationships for direct ink write materials design, *Prog. Mater. Sci.* (ISSN: 0079-6425) 140 (2023) 101188, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.pmatsci.2023.101188>.
- [62] Carlos F. Revelo, Henry A. Colorado, 3D printing of kaolinite clay ceramics using the direct ink writing (DIW) technique, *Ceram. Int.* (ISSN: 0272-8842) 44 (5) (2018) 5673–5682, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2017.12.219>.
- [63] Kwangwoo Wi, et al., Quantifying quality of 3D printed clay objects using a 3D structured light scanning system, *Addit. Manuf.* (ISSN: 2214-8604) 32 (2020) 100987, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2019.100987>.
- [64] Shuai Zhan, et al., 3D printing soft matters and applications: A review, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* (ISSN: 1422-0067) 23 (7) (2022) <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/ijms23073790>.
- [65] Abhishek Patel, Mohammad Taufik, Extrusion-based technology in additive manufacturing: A comprehensive review, *Arab. J. Sci. Eng.* (ISSN: 2191-4281) 49 (2) (2024) 1309–1342, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s13369-022-07539-1>.
- [66] Camila Friedman-Gerlicz, et al., WeaveSlicer: Expanding the range of printable geometries in clay, in: *Proceedings of the 2024 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, CHI '24, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, ISBN: 9798400703300, 2024, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/3613904.3642622>.
- [67] Jonathan King, *Guide to clay 3D printing*, 2020, URL http://keep-art.co.uk/Journal/JK_Guide_to_Clay_3D_Printing.pdf (Accessed: 2025-03-19).
- [68] V. Zukas, J.A. Zukas, *An Introduction to 3D Printing, First Edition Design eBook Publishing*, ISBN: 9781622878970, 2015.
- [69] J.M. Jordan, *3D printing, The MIT Press Essential Knowledge series*, MIT Press, ISBN: 9780262536684, 2019.
- [70] Erik Cuevas, et al., Setting up a 3D model for a 3D printer, in: *DC Motors: Modeling, Designing and Building with 3D Printers*, ISBN: 978-3-031-64354-5, 2025, pp. 157–172, http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-64354-5_6.
- [71] Mahan Motamedi, et al., Structural build-up of 3D printed earth by drying, *Addit. Manuf.* (ISSN: 2214-8604) 95 (2024) 104492, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2024.104492>.
- [72] Ofer Asaf, et al., From soil to printed structures: A systematic approach to designing clay-based materials for 3D printing in construction and architecture, *Constr. Build. Mater.* (ISSN: 0950-0618) 408 (2023) 133783, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2023.133783>.
- [73] Jacques Kruger, Stephan Zeranka, Gideon van Zijl, 3D concrete printing: A lower bound analytical model for buildability performance quantification, *Autom. Constr.* (ISSN: 0926-5805) 106 (2019) 102904, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2019.102904>.
- [74] Zeina Malaeb, Fatima AlSakka, Farook Hamzeh, Chapter 6 - 3D concrete printing: Machine design, mix proportioning, and mix comparison between different machine setups, in: Jay G. Sanjayan, Ali Nazari, Behzad Nematollahi (Eds.), *3D Concrete Printing Technology*, Butterworth-Heinemann, ISBN: 978-0-12-815481-6, 2019, pp. 115–136, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-815481-6.00006-3>.
- [75] Shoukat Alim Khan, et al., The impact of nozzle diameter and printing speed on geopolymer-based 3D-printed concrete structures: Numerical modeling and experimental validation, *Results Eng.* (ISSN: 2590-1230) 21 (2024) 101864, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2024.101864>.
- [76] Mihir Mogra, et al., Design optimization of 3D printed concrete elements considering buildability, *Eng. Struct.* (ISSN: 0141-0296) 294 (2023) 116735, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2023.116735>.
- [77] Gurminder Singh, et al., Copper additive manufacturing using MIM feedstock: adjustment of printing, debinding, and sintering parameters for processing dense and defectless parts, *Int. J. Adv. Manuf. Technol.* (ISSN: 1433-3015) 115 (1) (2021) 449–462, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00170-021-07188-y>.
- [78] *Czech Office for Standards, Metrology and Testing, European Norm EN 1927-5: Monolithic (unshaped) refractory products - Part 5: Preparation and treatment of the test pieces*, Tech. rep., (EN 1927-5) Czech Office for Standards, Metrology and Testing, Czech Republic, 2013.
- [79] Andrea Zocca, Jens Günster, Towards a debinding-free additive manufacturing of ceramics: A development perspective of water-based LSD and LIS technologies, *Open Ceram.* (ISSN: 2666-5395) 19 (2024) 100632, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.oceram.2024.100632>.
- [80] T. Ohji, M. Fukushima, Macro-porous ceramics: processing and properties, *Int. Mater. Rev.* 57 (2) (2012) 115–131, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1179/1743280411Y.0000000006>.
- [81] Necati Özkan, et al., Rheological analysis of ceramic pastes, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* (ISSN: 0955-2219) 19 (16) (1999) 2883–2891, [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0955-2219\(99\)00054-0](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0955-2219(99)00054-0).